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Digital divide and postmodern perspectives for new ICT access policies in developing societies: rethinking economism in the neo-imperial dystopian context

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Digital divide and postmodern perspectives for new ICT access policies in developing societies: rethinking economism in the neo-imperial dystopian context

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ABSTRACT

This paper set out to challenge the orthodox view that the problematic phenomenon of the digital divide is solely a matter of access to economic resources. This deterministic hypothesis suggests that by making resources available especially to Third World countries, the phenomenon would simply go away. The paper argues that, in as much as economic resources in sufficient quantities would be a desirable proposition because it would address *some* aspects of the problem, the phenomenon is much more complex and requires an integrative and holistic approach. Using the postmodernist theory to information and communication technologies, and resourcing data from a review of critical analyses, it comes to the conclusion that, beyond the metanarrative of economism that explains digital divide as a physical problem of access to computers, there are new and localizing narratives that range from new knowledge barriers, the human location of the digital gap, and definitional assumptions and issues, to questions of differentiation of benefits, disparity in big data promotion, material and social conditions of technological assimilation, international policy and cultural/moral factors and the class structure of society.

Keywords: Digital divide, ICT access, economism, post-modernism approach, gender outreach, nation state policies, morality of international cooperation, disability narratives, generational factors, re-embedding multiple layers of inequality

INTRODUCTION

A considerable amount of scholarship has emerged on the issue of the digital divide, but the assumptions that guide readings on the nature of the problem are often narrowly focused on economic causes (Stork and Gillwald 2013). Many misconceptions still abound about the possibilities of eliminating the phenomenon, even though there has been tremendous reduction in the prices of basic equipment for information and communication technologies (ICTs). This has enabled some members of the ordinary masses to access technology, but research carried out for more than fifty years now still betrays the persistence of the phenomenon and multiple inconsistencies in conceptual definitions. This paper is hypothesized on the premise that the phenomenon cannot be easily eliminated because the trends in the directions of digital divide have exploded into a constellation of ever expanding and irreversible new 'divides' based on new narratives like type of technology, educational skills, quality of cyberspace tools, class questions, morality, etc. From this light, *economism* is too narrow a criterion from which to understand, effect planning, evaluate, monitor and take decisions on the complex phenomenon of the 'digital divide'. The structuralist, Marxist-inspired method often deployed in scholarship does not possess sufficient explanatory power to account for the *momentum* of

the 'digital divide' in nation states entrenched in the imperial political economy of capitalism. Therefore, it is necessary to embed post-structuralist insights into the Marxist/liberal paradigm in order to potentialize its accountability for the persistence of this unfortunate cyberspace trend. A very obvious example of the digital divide is the stark disparity between citizens in Africa, Asia, Latin America and the Western industrialized countries. African nation state citizens have a very low access rate and, in some geographical areas, there is no access at all to digital technology and the internet. In 2013, it was only 8.6% of the total African population that had access to the internet whereas 81% of citizens in the US had access to the internet; this reflects an obviously wide gap not only in economic and social levels but also in terms of access to skills in technology (Stork and Gillwald 2013).

Theoretical framework and methodology

This paper draws from the postmodernist philosophical ontology in ICTs (Kroeze 2010) to investigate the complexity of this problem. Ontology is a philosophical paradigm that investigates the existential nature of things. In a particular philosophical epoch, there is usually only an acceptable ontology and the plurality of this concept is not envisioned. But in the universe of ICTs, ontology is pluralized as an option; it is endowed with a different meaning. Although both uses of the concept are logically and historically linked, the shift from a singular to a plural usage was accelerated by the postmodernist movement. The reality of ICTs has become fluid in the same way as meaning and knowledge are fleeting narratives. The development of software development has also undergone a philosophical modernist/postmodernist shift. This shift is a positive reality as the variegated character of ICT reality can also be signified by subsets of it. Although the formalism of ontologies is meant to capture and mirror reality, software that is ontology-based creates hyperrealities that may emerge as being more realistic than realism; in postmodernism, representations surface up to replace real life phenomena.

Contemporary society is in a turbulent condition as it is marked by fragmentation, individualism, pluralism, doubt, irony, and disillusionment (Nel and Kroeze 2008). As a metanarrative, modernism and its limitations opened the way to post-structuralism, nihilism and post-humanism. In the post-modern epoch, mankind turned to ICTs as an enabler. ICTs endowed it with great capabilities and this became a driving force as everyone sought to go online. This was what modernism meant: being familiar with cyberspace. However, instead of emancipating and uplifting mankind, ICTs brought consequences most of which were unforeseeable and unintended. ICTs did not bring the Utopia that was imagined, but rather engendered a world of indeterminacy, changes, virtuality, and continuous change, with its own information perspectives. ICTs promoted post-modernism by prioritizing the Information Society, displacing time and space, and constructing digital hyperrealities. The ontology of culture and tradition was erased and replaced by ontologies of identitarian revolution and catastrophe. Thus, to understand ICTs, one must understand the technology as a post-modernist agency. Under the postmodernism designation, ICTs respond to conditions that are portrayed as "pandemonic" and are quantitatively and qualitatively varying from 'facts' of the past (Braman 2003).

The paper shall draw from a critical review of literature on the digital divide as its source of data.

Determinism of digital divide

The term 'digital divide' was introduced in the mid-1990s as an interdisciplinary preoccupation in different circles of policy making, international cooperation and philanthropy. The concept assumes that the increasing 'gap' in digital technology access existing between, on the one hand, national communities in developing societies and, on the other hand, nations in industrialized countries, is determined chiefly by the economic factor, which induces social inequalities. The macro economic determinism behind this premise is that the more neoliberal capitalism expands into the 'capillaries' (households, communities, individuals, etc) within a developing nation-state and between nation-states, and geographical regions with their respective demographic categories, the more socio-cultural inequalities increase, and, consequently, the more the 'gap' divides those who have access to the means and benefits of ICTs and those who do not have such access nor such benefits. From this light, it is clear that this orthodox understanding, which positivizes the free market economy and its sequels such as widening income gaps, has infiltrated the 'problematic' of digital division in ICT access and benefits; however, it lacks a persuasive jurisdiction to illuminate the tenacity of the phenomenon and its embarrassment to policy makers, philanthropic organizations and international cooperation circles. This is so because the erroneous implication in this foundational paradigm is that a change in economic policy, alienating liberal capitalism, for example, would automatically induce an increase in revenue and this would, in turn, lead to a rise in the accessibility, usage and benefits of the digital technology to underprivileged communities. The further flawed implication in this rather essentialistic understanding is that the existence of economism barriers, poverty and the resultant social inequality is responsible for slicing off people's accessibility to cyberspace technology usage, benefits and overall impact. This deterministic principle behind the digital gap/ divide between nation states of the world, and in the international scale of developed and undeveloped countries, is too reductionist as an assumption to be accepted.

The chief economic determinant of the digital gap is information technology access; but, the issue of accessibility is not the only criterion of measurement, there is also the bigger question of utilization and even the question of reception. Following this *economistic* trajectory, Western industrialized countries easily access the cyberspace technology, while Africa, Latin America and Asia have very serious hurdles with accessibility. The irony here is in the logical thinking that by supplying the cyberspace technology to Third World countries in sufficient quantities, the problem of accessibility would necessarily be resolved once and for all. However, this problem cannot be resolved once and for all by simply transposing the digital technology to 'peripheral' countries because, if this was the way out, philanthropic organizations in the West would have applied this *economism* model extensively. The reality is that people have to obtain knowledge on *how to utilize* the information that they acquire from the internet. Third world countries have had the serious challenge of dealing with illiteracy since the years of independence: so, for instance, the majority of Africans cannot be able to utilize computers, even if they received them free. In addition, digital technology is not merely a physical object, it is a culture; so, nationals have to be *receptive* to the internet information. The reactions of receptionists (e.g. likes, anticipation, expectations of messages, finding time, etc) can be even more critical than the cold indifference of technological presence.

The new knowledge barriers

In the course of the decades, and with reduction in the gaps not only in the terms of economic revenue, but also of lessening of gaps in the light of gender, race, education and age, there has been a gradual paradigmatic shift from the digital divide (understood as *economism*) to a more formidable problem of *knowledge* divide. More and more people can now access digital technology; however, the increasing hurdle is that they are confronted with the problematic of *how to utilize, interpret* and deploy information and knowledge. This, so-called 'second generation of digital divide', which is also referred to as the 'production gap', has to do with the gap between consumers and producers of digital content. In this stage, the focus has been shifting toward new questions of *how to deploy* the digital technology in order to construct content and how this shaped user compoment. The digital divide has been shifting from an *economistic* gap in ICT connectivity and accessibility to a gap in the knowledge divide (Graham 2011). In the knowledge divide stage, the gap shifted further beyond accessibility to the capacity to possess mental resources for ICT connectivity, interpretation and comprehension of information. There are millions of blogs that were created by users; but these blogs were made by a minimal percentage of internet users. Facebook, Instagram and Twitter enable users to exploit the internet without them having any knowledge of the digital technology and how it works. Although *economism* and social inequalities may play a role here, users of lower economic and social status may be less likely to deploy the internet technology. So, the point being made here is that the 'digital divide' may construct a totally new, independent and autonomous narrative called 'information or knowledge divide' which is alienating from *economism* and reflects the level of information and knowledge acquisition about the world, its environment, protection issues and so forth. The next point from this understanding is that this new, independent and autonomous narrative of absence of information and knowledge may also, in its own turn, reconstruct economic and social development in various nation state communities.

The production gap separates 'producers' of knowledge from consumers of 'content' (Reilley 2011). Even with the lessening of the digital divide in terms of users who enjoy accessibility to the Internet and users who do not enjoy such an accessibility, the meaning of the term digital divide is now growing and evolving. Beyond how users deploy the Internet to construct content, is the new question of how content impacts upon socioeconomic status and how this, in turn, influences user compoment (Graham 2014: 189-195). With new digital applications, any computer user who is connected to the internet can construct content, but much of the user-generated content in blogs, Web 2.0 technologies like YouTube, Facebook, Twitter, etc, is created by a very small minority of the Internet population and this has been leading to an ever-augmented digital divide between users who possess understanding and skills to interact more fully with digital technology and users who passively consume such knowledge. This minority of nominal creators of content typically post pictures and update their status on Facebook, without necessarily being immersed in the technology.

The human location of the gap

Now, the critical question is: where is the *location* of this production gap? The answer is that it has shifted from the *economism* of access to a new material narrative of factors such as *type* of Internet connection that a user has, *frequency* of Internet access, *speed* of Internet connection, and so on. Thus, beyond technology access is the new question of type, frequency, and speed of connectivity, which has the potential to open up opportunities to gain more time to be creative and sharpen technology skills (Chradie 2011). In addition, economic and social status engendered class divisions that manifested in developing societies in terms of cultural attitudes. Consequently, users of the lower class of socioeconomic status did not have the propensity to take part in content creation as a result of important hurdles like illiteracy, lack of free time to devote to websites and blogs, patience with breakdowns in the

technology and so forth (Chradie2011: 145–168).The second-level phase of digital divide (K-12 level) also evidence the fact that the deployment of the technology by teachers for purposes of instruction is varied depending on whether it is for basic information gathering or it is for development of thinking skills of the higher-order (Reinhart, Toriskie and Thomas 2011).

Definitional assumptions and issues

Much discussion on the subject matter of the digital divide itself has become a never ending narrative that has taken multiple discursive directions in terms of causes, methods, management, solutions, etc. These directions take the form of instructional technology whether in schools and universities, state offices, communities, corporate bodies, bridging the gap and issues of impact through policy (Kvasny andKeil2006, Kvasny 2006, Sassi2005). The discussions are materialized in scientific papers (Bucy 2000, Gunkel 2003, Hoffman, Novak, and Schlosser 2000, Kanungo 2004, Wresch 1996) published book debates (Compaine 2001, Bolt and Crawford 2000, Ebo1998, Walsh 2000, Warschauer 2003, Lax2001) and in general Internet circles. The focus shifts from conceptualization of the digital divide metanarrative towards bridging the gap or even closing the divide altogether. The debates are organized by foundations like the Pew Internet and American Life Project (2003), the U.S. Department of Commerce and National Telecommunications and Information Administration and the UN. A number of positions are held in the debates such as that the digital divide is worsening as time goes on (Hacker and Mason 2003),the divide is on course to close on its own, and that the incorporation of digital technology in school and university education is aggravating the inequalities between classes of people (Selwyn, Gorard and Williams 2001). The implication from these definitional issues is that the eradication of inequalities in technological access is contingent upon the elimination of inequalities in schools and university education as well as in the wider contextual discussions of the digital divide. This confirms our hypothesis that the postcolonial contexts of knowledge, culture, education, and even how the digital divide is defined can also reconstruct technological access; it is not merely economic and social inequalities of classes. Thus, we reiterate the thesis that it is necessary to re-conceptualize the digital divide, even though some analysis of it will be provided; our purpose here is to examine the implicit assumptions that appear to be the underpinnings to the discourse of “closing” and “bridging” the digital divide. In other words, while we agree that equal distribution of educational digital opportunities is desirable, we are curious why so many policymakers, politicians, CEOs, scholars, and educators suddenly became so concerned about the digital divide in the late 1990s and in the early years of the new millennium. After all, lack of access to computers and Internet technologies is not different from the multiples of inequities that people from dominated and underrepresented groups experience in terms of access to education and to the world’s resources overall, and there is no same concern over such inequities.

The world is full of multiples of types of divisive narratives that merit attention; for example, beyond the economic factors of the digital divide, there are others like the ‘healthy life’ divide, ‘the labour/working conditions’ divide, the gender divide, the ‘core’, semi-periphery’ and ‘periphery’ divide, etc, which separate peoples and nation states. These forms of nation state division and their sequels are multiple but the political, socio-cultural and economic environments tend to prioritize the digital ‘divide’ as opposed to the continuous incidence of other divides on society. Thus, this paper suggests that beyond the economism underpinning the digital ‘divide’, the larger context that defines divides all over the world founded on class, gender, race, and nation should be considered (Luyt 2004). The cultural capital of people who have accessed and developed skills is increased by prioritizing the divide, but the outcomes from this are unpredictable and undecidable because there is a difference between digital divide and digital inequality. There is *access* to the digital technology, but beyond this, there is also the problem of *equitability in the gains* that come with digital access. Therefore, social inequalities all over the world push beneficiaries like governments, international organizations and businesses to stress on erasure of the digital divide (Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development 2004, Kvasny 2006).

Differentiation of benefits

There is differentiation rather than equality in levels of benefits: benefits derived from the infusion and impact of ICTs on economic growth and productivity are given a different interpretation from readings of benefits to underrepresented groups of people and marginalized classes. So, the concept of ‘benefit’is itself an ambivalent narrative. It is not put on the table in the same way: digital benefits for subaltern classes are discussed in the light of ‘no one should be left behind’, threat of losing out on skills, job security, (Kvasny and Truex 2001: 399-415), etc. Digital benefits for governments, corporations, international organizations and businesses are read in terms of economic efficiency. As a result of these discrepancies in the two ‘benefits’, there were ‘unintended consequences’ (Keil and Kvasny 2006: 27).Although it is difficult to define ‘intention’, the ‘un-intentions’ behind the ‘consequences’ caused further harm to whatever benefits were derived and also protected the interests of certain classes of people over other classes. The ‘consequences’ translated into, reconstructed or justified the rhetoric of the digital divide, and

the ideology behind educational and social inequalities, as political economics created its own ideological relationship to society. Antonio Gramsci (1981) theorized about the ideological hegemony that sustains elite classes over subaltern ones and came to the conclusion that a dominant group needs to continuously replicate its power structure so that the *status quo* can be perpetuated. The Gramscian notion theorizes ideological hegemony as a form of power that nourishes not only political and repressive authority but also moral, thought and intellectual leadership. In this way, ideology constructs coercive, moral, intellectual and cultural power, which in turn confers privileges to any one social class over another class. Beyond the material historicism of economism, which constructs repressive power, is the Gramscian preoccupation with ideology in industrialized nation states. Authority is an ambiguous narrative that is exercised not only through physical institutions such as the military, security forces, the police, etc, thanks to economic resources of access, but is also sustained through science, education, culture and technology, which are redistributive of new social imperatives, norms and values (Gramsci 1972). In this Gramscian re-contextualization of Marxian economic class structure, intellectuals reconstruct themselves into a powerful hegemonic class interest that may ally with the ruling elite interest or may de-solidarize and re-constitute itself into a separate autonomous system. This analysis should therefore enable us to consider popularization of the digital divide discourse as a product not merely of economic access but also of ideological hegemony sustained by the intelligentsia class.

Disparity in big data promotion

The digital divide is a dynamic and complex phenomenon related to the ideologization of hegemonic divisiveness, and the ambivalence of the digital divide metanarrative framed as big data discrepancy (Ono and Zavodny 2007). The persistence of the divide can be explained not only in terms of poverty in the provision of ICTs respectively in rich and low-resourced nation states but also in terms of disparity in big data promotion. Big data 'digital divide' betrays disproportionality in the availability of data, information and knowledge. But connected to this gap is the range of additional skills that are a requisite condition for an efficient distribution as spelled out in Amartya Sen's 'capabilities approach'. Sen's 'capabilities approach' distinguishes between, on the one hand, making available resources – which align with economic access - and, on the other hand, fostering capabilities to deploy the resources. We recognize that this perspective is illuminating but it needs further exploration and expansion (Ndi 2011). The alternative capabilities orientation provides an insight that explains the persistence of profound inequalities in the universal data landscape that appears to be founded on an egalitarian principle. This capability (e.g. Cloud technologies, Hadoop, digital languages, development and architectural skills, etc) and the skills necessary to share data and enforce its applications (artificial intelligence, lots, driverless automobiles, augmented reality, etc) is disproportionate in Northern and Southern countries. Consequently, the capability to share data efficiently and productively is contingent on the ability to construct a heterogeneous rather than a dichotomized research environment. Southern countries are now paying increasing attention to the deployment efficiency of ICTs through progressive improvements in capabilities of constructs such as knowledge leveraging, access, adoption, acquisition, innovation, management, diffusion, exploitation, and institutionalism through databases. The implications for this kind of research are the need to distinguish technology, data and knowledge management. Knowledge is data/information processed via a user's brain; it is a new insight with possibilities of modification and predictive understanding, a combination of context, information and experience, and a prescription of knowing what to do (Bohn 1994). The achievement of information and knowledge is primordial in any quest of a nation state to take accurate decisions on the use and application of technologies. This kind of strategic insight is necessary to reach the different phases of digital efficiency from a narrowly management perspective involving state and corporate leadership to a stage of coordinated effort in order to deploy technological knowledge and learning. The expectation is that Third World countries will strive to achieve technodigital knowledge so as to overcome the digital divide and realize new competences in digital technology (Kogut and Zander 1992, Kvasny 2006, Kvasny and Keil 2006).

Material and social conditions of technological assimilation

Beyond the digital divide scholarship that is often narrowed down to technodigital access and penetration in Third World nation states, is the critical question of material, social conditions of technological assimilation by the middle, intelligentsia class. As a result of the uneven distribution of ICT connectivity, a new narrative of positive/negative influence was generated in which the digital technology opened up possibilities for higher education but at the same time, the digital divide closed up those possibilities by minimizing students' participation in distance education. In some countries like Indonesia (like in most Third World nation states), distance education is available to students in the capital cities and towns whereas in more peripheral areas like villages, students do not gain a lot of benefit from the employment of this new technology, although these peripheral regions need them for their development. In the capital cities and towns, the new technology appears to empower the learning activities of students and to contribute to their study environments more efficiently (Stale Angen Rye, 2008).

International policy and cultural/moral factors

The information and communication technology is based on neoliberal capitalism, which itself has constructed different forms of the digital divide, understood as the outcome of the inherent asymmetry existing in the structural processes of economic, political, and cultural accumulation that has engendered structural inequalities. In Nigeria, for instance, the World Bank and IMF policies of privatization and liberalization worsened the problematic of digital divide and only an integrative approach can begin to address it effectively. With a billion persons out of the world's six billion people living on less than a dollar every day; with two billion persons living on less than three dollars everyday, and with the relatively better conditions of poor people in industrialized nation states, it is understandable that the digital divide literature is often discussed in terms of material access. However, there are cultural and moral factors that also play into this structurally economic picture. Material poverty in many nation states of the world is often linked unjustifiably to evidence of cultural laziness, and moral unworthiness. People who are poor have to go through not only the physical pain of hunger, but also internalize the psychological pain of disrespectability. This unfortunate cultural perception and the sense of denial of rights that comes with it, leads to the denial of rights as well when it comes to technological access, which is a requisite condition for improvement of human conditions.

In developed nation states, there is no convergence of views between conservatives and liberals over this important issue of assistance to the poor. While in a general sense, conservatives believe it is not their responsibility to save lives, liberals think the opposite that life should be protected. Admittedly, opinions divulge when one looks at the detailed specifics between classes of people motivated by these differing ideological philosophies. Nevertheless, the point being made here is that these conflicting ideological positions have impacted negatively on the accessibility issue in developing countries of the world. With increasing poverty in Third World countries marked by absence of clean water, malnutrition, illiteracy, and poor health care facilities, the provision of digital technology is seen as a misplaced moral priority. The challenge is for citizens in industrialized countries to come to a consensus on re-embedding moral responsibility and the fight against poverty. The reading of poverty should not be narrowly focused only on economics, but should integrate its narrative sequels, namely, moral obligations, education, globalization barriers, waiving of particular intellectual rights, exposure to conditions of bare life, and their cumulative effects such as the digital divide and information gap.

The class structure of society

The new forms of digital divide that have emerged now are related to new 'classes' of people such as elderly persons, disabled persons, women, and children. In relation to elderly persons, it is called the 'grey digital divide' as aged people have become the new 'victims' of technology access (Holtfreter et al., 2015). This is particularly acute in developing countries and necessitates a rethinking of the digital divide concept (Jenkins 2006). Women in developing nation states enjoy a relatively lower rate of participation in digital technology as compared to men. This is owing to socio-culturally entrenched sensitivities and attitudes about women's place in many societies (Hafkin et al, 2007, Moolman, J., Primo and Shackleton, 2007, Hafkin and Taggart, 2001, Dugdale 2013, Weingarten 2013, Heavey 2013 Clauss et al. 2013, Gill et al. 2010, Strohlic 2014). This factor has no direct link with liberal capitalism but is rather a cultural and anthropological reality that existed even prior to imperial and colonial rule. Nevertheless, women can still engage with the digital technology, and, in this case, what is important is that a number of benefits can accrue from such an engagement at the levels of community, family and personal needs. On-line education access, for example, can trigger a positive feedback loop. Gender discrepancy in the employment of the technology and access barriers to online world participation must be dealt with as potential opportunity to alleviate gender bias in these nation states rather than as a problem. The digital divide phenomenon thrives in circular causation as a result of the 'skill gap' leading to a gap in physical access to ICTs (Kularski 2012:5). Access to digital technology is a requisite condition for development of technical skill; but, as well, digital technology cannot be accessed without the first precondition of possessing the skills to deploy it.

Discrepancies in digital access exacerbated the digital divide between offline and online users (Kularski 2012: 359) and of gap between users who have accessed resources of ICTs and those who have not. This divide extended beyond the offline/online communities, to incorporate the disparity between rich/poor people, the technological gap between industrialized/undeveloped countries and the physically abled/disabled men and women within them (Norris 2001). The digital divide has extended to foreground a democratic divide separating persons who deploy digital resources to mobilize and engage populations in politics and persons who do not employ such resources to partake in public life. Now, digital access engages with material, psychological, usage and skills factors that have little to do with belonging to the universe of 'have-nots' and 'haves' (Van Dijk and Hacker 2003). Psychologically, people may not be interested to gain access to the technology or may develop a negative sensitivity and predisposition to computers as opposed to users who do not have such feelings. Physical infrastructure, literacy skills in the use of the digital equipment and the opportunity or time factors may be primordial in determining the

divide. In addition to the gaps at national/global and local/community levels owing to applications, attitudes, access and awareness factors, there is the knowledge gap hypothesis. This hypothesis postulates that individuals who enjoy an elevated economic and social status will discover new sources of information that others without such a status will not be predisposed to find. This can then motivate their purpose for usage of the technology such as autonomy of use, socio-economic status.

From these examples, the concept of 'access' in the context of digital divide has been shifting from 'connection' to the technology to 'employment', 'choice', 'opportunity' and this has compromised the sense in which one can speak of 'inequality of technology access' (DiMaggio et al., 2004: 355-400). Although the term digital divide in the economic perspective has preserved its denotative meaning, that meaning is watered down by contextual evidence like psychological motivation, cultural construction of gender prejudices, skills, knowledge, technophobia, etc. It has become less helpful to investigate the digital divide phenomenon simply by binarizing classifications of digital "haves" and ICT "haves". Even when the digital products are provided as a matter of policy and philanthropy, such an effort cannot ensure that people will all of a sudden acquire knowledge, integrate into inclusive gender, generational and disability spaces, or gain psychological motivation and predisposition to enjoy the benefits that the technology proffers.

There is a need to re-conceive the discussion on digital divide by recognizing that inequality is a complex phenomenon that impacts on skills and connectivity barriers. Thus, beyond the economic, digital technologies have assimilated socio-cultural and psychological processes, not merely at the entry, outsidepoint to the internet but also within the cyberspace itself. The increasing number of barriers to digital content has to do not directly with economics but with code regulation, policy decisions and models of co-regulation. This requires multiple forms of control of public goods that exist beyond institutions of law if the quest for the public goal of technological welfare is to be achieved. The Information Society, which is a World Summit, should integrate the digital divide not merely as economic access but as a challenge to content access that compromises user participation and minimizes the social and nation state implications of digital technologies. ICTs have the prospective to boost the power of people to realize an egalitarian contribution to world citizenship. This is a possibility for persons with intellectual disability. Nevertheless, the way that the digital technology is designed is a very challenging experience for these people and that a digital divide has gradually formed between them and the connected citizen and therefore there is a need to consider future research that embeds other dimensions in the design of the technology to promote digital inclusion and participation of intellectually disabled persons. These new dimensions may include and were identified: access to digital devices, sensorimotor, cognitive and technical requirements and the comprehension of codes and conventions.

Intellectual disability is a situation marked by impairments in adaptive behaviour intellectual functions and this condition may extend to expressive skills at social, conceptual and practical levels and in any age. This condition prevails in about 1% to 3% of the overall population (United Nations, 2012). When it comes to the context of ICT use, skills and exploitation, the situation becomes complex because of multiple physical factors that become barriers such as their sensorimotor. In addition, the environment of intellectual disability can also become disabling in itself as interactions with people may lead to stigmatization, alienation and avoidance. The challenge, then, is how persons with intellectual disability, in particular and persons with disabilities, in general, can be empowered socially through their access to, but more especially, their use of the technology. The digital technology has the potential to ameliorate social participation, self-determination and life quality for persons with disability (Chadwick 2013). This potential also needs not only new technological designs, but also new social frameworks and courageous state policies. Lastly, barriers to information access go beyond the economic to include challenges confronted by visually impaired persons in the era of the information and communication revolution (Palmer et al., 2012, Parsons 2008, Perkins and LaMartin2012). This new paradigm of 'information technology inequity' is holistic and stresses marginalization from a cross-cultural perspective. The digital disablement of visually impaired persons whether in Africa, India or the US has to do with cultural, political, psychological and educational factors of marginalization (Chaudhry2005)

CONCLUSION

The results of this investigation show that the concept of 'digital divide' is a very complex phenomenon than was previously comprehended differently because, beyond its economism origins as physical access, it has the potential to generate a multiplicity of narratives of 'gaps' with their own possible effects. Even though developed nation states have bypassed developing nation states in the light of cyberspace infrastructure and penetration, a number of important digital divides have survived in these regions as well. Economic and social class indicators are too narrow and deterministic a perspective from which to consider ICT nation state relationships all over the world. Based on these findings, this paper suggests that a systematic way out of the complexity of the problem is to ensure an adequate minimization of the digital divide would require efforts at multiple levels as outlined above. In order to

efficiently address the phenomenon, focus should not be laid solely on ICTs as technology of capital; rather, it should expand to ICTs in social welfare, healthcare, promotion of culture, morality, disability (Ndi 2012) and other practical agenda all over the world, by drawing extended insights, ideas and knowledge from them.

In terms of postcolonial digital perspectives for the future of persons with disabilities, this paper suggests strongly that there are new areas that can be explored (Liyanagunawardena et al. 2013). Beyond the need for new technological designs for computers, for example, that are accessible and adaptive, it is critical that insights from the environmental contexts of interaction (Ndi 2012) should be investigated so as to align them with the possibilities of designing new architectures for the digital technology. This alignment can draw from insights that have to do with the cyberspace as a narrative of assistance, an expressive culture, facilitator of independence and life skills or safety. From the light of disabled children, the digital divide is not only a question of economic access, it is also an issue of addressing barriers in communication needs, digital design, acceptability and use, linguistic access, skills and sensor-motor and safety of use. Digital access in the sense of 'opportunity' may go along with reading skills, physical and mobility limitations and the need for cognitive skills. Digital developers have to show sensitivity not only to disability types, but also to different disability experiences, new issues of performance abilities, functionality, autonomy of usage, eye trackability and selectivity of certain disabilities, learning efficiency, ease of navigation, digital assistance and usage guides. They have to consider questions of oral support and modeling. Usage for disabled users is an idea that takes multiple forms. It can be usage of the digital technology in everyday life, or usage as perceived from reports of family members. There are safety issues that may take the form of risk in the context of cyberspace solicitations or risks in terms of pre-existing health conditions like disorders. Efficiency of technological support is a form of accessibility that can take the form of functionality rather than economic access (Rivas-Costas et al. 2014), or mental recognition (Rocha et al. 2012). Dating possibilities (Sallafranque St-Louis 2015) and the perception of online risks (Seale 2014), perceptions in usage (Shpigelman 2016, Shpigelman and Gill 2014, Sigafos et al. 2005, Stephenson and Limbrick 2015), may also emerge usage in survey reports (Tanis et al. 2012). There is accessibility in a technical sense of design (Stock et al. 2006) and even in the sense of use of ICTs in service provision (Taber-Doughty et al 2010).

Sketch bio

Alfred Ndi holds a *Doctorat d'État* Degree with research interests in digital capitalism and the ideas industry. He investigates how imperial online *signifiers* of capital intersect with knowledge production in the largest sense of political economy and interfaces further with postcolonial critical discourses to spawn power crisis in ICT technologies and cultures.

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